

**BEYOND BORDERS: A STUDY OF FOREIGN ENGLISH TEACHERS'
PERCEPTIONS ON GENDER DYNAMICS IN EFL STUDENTS' INTEREST AND
INVOLVEMENT IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING IN UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract. *Uzbekistan, distinguished as a preeminent nation among Central Asian countries, has undertaken a huge project to provide exemplary language education to its school-level students by recruiting qualified foreign English teachers (FETs). The observed differences between male and female students in the realm of English language acquisition prompted an identification of a research gap, subsequently leading to the formulation of the research question: To ascertain which gender, male or female students, demonstrates greater interest in English language learning and active participation in related educational activities.*

Quantitative data, obtained through a structured questionnaire, underwent thorough appropriate analysis. The ensuing findings reveal an evident trend wherein a majority of female students express heightened interest across various facets of English language acquisition, encompassing reading, writing, listening, speaking, vocabulary, pronunciation, and grammar. Furthermore, a notable proportion of female students actively engage in language-learning-related curricular and extracurricular activities.

It is imperative to underscore the fact that the objective of this study is not to perpetuate gender-based discrimination but rather to elucidate and underscore significant implications for the enhancement of the learning environment for both male and female students.

Keywords: *Uzbekistan, Language education, Gender differences, English language learning, Learning environment*

Introduction:

Among the captivating Central Asian nations, Uzbekistan stands out as a remarkably beautiful country, offering significant advantages for learners, particularly in the realm of English language acquisition. The ministry of education of the republic of Uzbekistan has recruited Foreigners as English Teachers or Foreign English Teachers (FETs) to teach English to Uzbek children at schools. The aim of this huge project is to improve the English proficiency among the children consequently; it will enhance the knowledge of English among the generation to come easily and as a result, Uzbek Vision to be hegemonic in various aspect becomes realistic. The researcher, during the pre-observation could see that in majority of the secondary classes, there are more female students in the classroom than male students. In addition, it was further obvious that female students show more interest in learning almost in all subjects. While primary grades have approximately equal number of gender balance. Female students are seen outshining in their academic performances in various levels. Recent researchers show a great deal of interest in the impact of gender on language learning [1] in terms of L1, EFL and ESL context [2], [3]. Learners' individual differences can be categorized used different types, according to Oxford's Learning Strategies, gender difference and learning strategy includes (a) memory strategy, (b), cognitive strategy, (c) compensation strategy, (d) metacognitive strategy, (e) affective strategy and (f) social strategy [4]. Individual Differences in learning and teaching can be divided into various views such as complex, dynamic, socio-ecological and holistic view. Individual differences in terms of language learning and teaching, it includes Motivation, Strategies, Aptitude, Positive beliefs,

Autonomy, Personality, Style, Age, Affect/emotions, feelings, Gender, Culture / nationality / ethnicity / race [5]. Uzbekistan is committed to advancing contemporary knowledge and education by 2025. To realize this objective, the government is actively enlisting exceptionally skilled teachers, mentors, professors, and genuine intellectuals. These individuals are expected to possess the capabilities necessary to assume responsibility for the present and future development of Uzbekistan, shaping the destiny of the country's youth [6]. As the world acknowledges the significance of gender-inclusive education, understanding how these dynamics manifest in language learning becomes not only a scholarly pursuit but a practical necessity for educators and policymakers. Previous research has identified gender-based variations in language learning styles and preferences [7]. Uzbekistan government implemented a policy wherein they reimburse the examination fees for all students. The condition stipulates that candidates under the age of 30 will receive a refund of approximately 200 USD if they achieve a score of band 7 or higher. Additionally, if a candidate under the age of 16 attains a score beyond band 7, their parents become eligible for the exam fee reimbursement. It's noteworthy that this reimbursement policy extends beyond the IELTS test to include TOEFL scores of 95 or higher, GMAT and GRE scores of 75% or higher, and SAT scores of 1200 or above [8]. This study aligns with the broader discourse on gender, education, and language acquisition contributing to growing body of knowledge among Uzbek school EFL learners.

Objective of the study

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the inclinations of male and female students in Uzbekistan concerning their engagement in English language learning. Specifically, the research places emphasis on assessing the preferences of both genders regarding the acquisition of Vocabulary, Grammar, Pronunciation, Speaking, Listening, Reading, and Writing skills. Additionally, the study delves into the examination of the enthusiasm exhibited by male and female students in adhering to regular attendance, active participation in classroom activities, and the completion of assigned homework as per instructional directives.

It is pertinent to note that the scope of this paper is limited to students attending school and does not extend to the consideration of undergraduate students, candidates enrolled in IELTS-like course programs, those pursuing higher studies, or vocational education. Furthermore, it is essential to underscore that this study does not intend to discriminate against gender differences among students.

Literature review

The implementation of inclusive education in schools is supported by Article 20 of the recently enacted Law on Education (2020). Furthermore, the President's decree #4860 in October 2020 not only approved the concept but also outlined a roadmap for the gradual introduction of inclusive education across all mainstream schools in Uzbekistan by 2025 [9]. The socio-cultural context and motivating educational policies create a unique environment for enhancing English language learning dynamics [10]. Foreign English teachers in Uzbekistan contribute significantly to the multifaceted nature of English language education. Their cultural diversity, pedagogical approaches, and linguistic competence enrich the learning experience.

A study of 50 male and female students' effect of gender on language learning concluded that, it unequivocally showed that success rate of total female learners was better compared to male learners. Female pupils are better second language learners. Moreover, EFL instructors should enhance their awareness of gender effects and strive to be well-versed in the distinctions between male and female learners [11].

Gender difference in Indonesian school was investigated and conclusion shed light on the fact that gender differences are an important aspect in English language teaching [12]. Another study in American College of Management in Dubrovnik, Croatia concluded the study on the use of strategy in terms of gender in learning L2 further witnessed that female students exhibited a higher frequency of utilizing learning strategies compared to their male counterparts [13]. Female students in Saudi Arabia also exhibited more interest compared to male learners [14].

As a turning point, a study among Taiwanese students concluded that female students show more interest in certain areas that are related to females while men showed considerable interest in all areas [15]. Male and female students showed similar behaviour in partaking lexical learning although small changes were observed among adolescent learners showed small variation in physiological and psychological aspect as well as in motivation [16]. In contrast, despite gender variation, both male and female students paid equal attention to the learning of reading, it slightly supports [15] in the fact that female students pay more attention on reading female type of reading materials [17].

In absolute contrast, a study was carried out in India proved that male students are more motivated than female as male students are more concerned about their qualification and employability unlike female [18]. Adding more value to the point another study in China unveiled the fact that female learners seek help from peer and teacher to a greater extend compared to male students [19].

Gap and Significance

Male students do undoubtedly perform well in professional qualification and undergraduate, postgraduate, doctoral as well as professorial careers. It does not mean female candidates are weaker than man is or otherwise, female students in school perform extraordinarily well in school level education and thus, it does not show that boys are lower than girl students are. In examining the complex interplay between foreign English teachers' perceptions, gender dynamics, and students' interest in English language learning within the Uzbekistan context, this study explores the gender differences in aspects like both male and female learners interest in learning Vocabulary, Grammar, Pronunciation, Speaking, Listening, Reading, and Writing. On top of that, the study further concentrates on the interest of both male and female students' interest in attending classes on a regular basis, taking part in classroom activities as well as doing the homework as instructed by the teacher. Although there are several research work have been already carried out on this topic, there is hardly any research in this sample region on this FET's perception on gender difference in learning EFL. Therefore, this paper will serve learners, teachers, policy makers and authorities in as many ways as possible. It's vitally important to mention that the researcher doesn't intend to discriminate gender based learners proficiency but to bring forth insights that teachers, policy makers and concerned parties to school education consider the fact found in the finding section so that the variation in learning among both male and female students shall be dealt in a productive way.

Methodology:

This study employs a quantitative research design to investigate foreign English teachers' perceptions of gender dynamics in EFL students' interest in English language learning in Uzbekistan. The chosen design aligns with the exploratory nature of the research question, aiming to capture the richness and depth of teachers' experiences and perspectives.

Participants and data collection

The participants in this study will consist of 10 foreign English teachers currently working in government schools across Tashkent city in Uzbekistan. Data were collected through a Google form in the form of multiple choice grid type questions. The questions investigate both male and female learners' interest and involvement in learning English in school setting. As far as learners' interest is concerned, the researcher aimed at investigating learners' interest in increasing vocabulary, learning grammar, enhancing pronunciation, practicing more speaking, listening to English, improving reading skills, and developing writing proficiency. Likewise, regular attendance to English classes, taking part in English classroom activities as well as doing homework are given importance in terms of learners involvement.

Instruments and Data Analysis

The research will apply a structured survey instrument to quantify definite aspects of foreign English teachers' perceptions and experiences on Gender Dynamics in EFL Students' Interest in English Language Learning in Uzbekistan. Moreover, the survey questions were developed based on the identified themes from the review of existing literature, as well as researcher's pre-observation on the research problem. Besides, all quantitative data collected through Google form were analyzed using MS Excel 2016 and IBM SPSS 22 in order to derive descriptive analysis from the data.

Findings and Discussion

The researcher has divided the findings into two segments such as learners' interest in learning English and learners' involvement in improving language skills and proficiency. Firstly, the findings of the study on Uzbek EFL learners' interest in developing vocabulary, improving grammar knowledge, acquiring sound pronunciation, leaning speaking skills, listening to English to understand native speakers accurately, enhancing reading skills, and gaining writing proficiency. And followed by that pupils' involvement in learning English under regular attendance to English classes, taking part in English classroom activities as well as doing homework properly are evaluated.

Learners' interest

Despite male student outshine in academic career better than female, as school level students, female pupils witnessed showing more interest in learning English.

Figure 1. Pupils' interest in Learning English

In the context of pupils' engagement with English language acquisition, empirical data indicates a discernible disparity in interest between male and female students. Specifically, there is a marked inclination among female students to exhibit heightened interest in honing various language skills. Pronunciation, speaking, and writing skills demonstrate a distinct gender-related difference, with a significant preference of 90% among females compared to a modest 10% among males. In contrast, vocabulary, grammar, listening, and reading skills show a comparatively more balanced distribution, ranging between 60 to 70 percent among female students, while their male counterparts exhibit a lower preference, ranging from 30 to 40 percent.

Learners' involvement

Certainly! Here's a more academically toned version:

In contrast to technical disciplines, the acquisition of a language necessitates heightened engagement and participation on the part of students.

Figure 2. Pupils' involvement in Learning English

As far as students' participation in educational endeavors, encompassing regular attendance, active engagement in both curricular and extracurricular classroom activities, and diligent completion of assignments are concerned, female students exhibited a notable commitment, indicating proportions of 90%, 80%, and 90% respectively. Conversely, male students demonstrated a comparatively lower inclination, with levels of interest ranging from 10% to 20% in all aspects pertinent to active participation in learning activities and completion of homework assignments.

Comparison with Existing Literature

The findings of the present study align with and contribute to the existing body of literature on gender variation in language acquisition. This is consistent with the observations made in a study examining the impact of gender on language learning, involving 50 male and female students in Iran [11]. Additionally, congruent findings have been documented in studies conducted in an Indonesian school [12], the American College of Management in Dubrovnik, Croatia [13], and among female students in Saudi Arabia, where a discernible proclivity for language learning was observed in comparison to their male counterparts [14]. Similarly, a study involving Taiwanese students posited that female students exhibited a heightened interest in specific domains associated with femininity, while male students demonstrated a noteworthy interest across diverse areas [15].

Conversely, a distinct study [16] reported equitable levels of interest among both male and female students.

Conversely, a study conducted in India presented contrasting results, asserting that male students displayed greater motivation and focus in learning foreign languages compared to their female counterparts. This discrepancy was attributed to male students' heightened concern for qualifications and employability, in contrast to female students [18]. Adding further depth to this perspective, a study in China revealed that female learners sought assistance from peers and teachers to a greater extent when compared to their male counterparts [19]."

Discussion of Implications

It is imperative to underscore that the aforementioned observations neither segregate nor diminish the academic performance of male students. Notably, the IELTS Niners ratio in Uzbekistan contradicts any notion of a disparity between male and female performance, revealing an opposite outcome. This study bears significant implications for EFL education and educators in Uzbekistan. Acknowledging and addressing school level EFL learners' difference in English language learning and varied mindset towards involving in learning curricular and extracurricular activities is crucial. By considering the variation between male and female students in school level setting, it is important for teachers to contribute more balanced and engaging learning experience. Undoubtedly, teachers are pivotal in shaping the educational landscape, with a crucial responsibility to foster an egalitarian and motivational learning environment. While it is essential to acknowledge that male students are not inherently weaker, the observed variance in motivation levels necessitates attention. This phenomenon, however, is not universally applicable to all male students.

Conclusion

The act of teaching a male student can be likened to the cultivation of an individual, whereas educating a female holds a parallel significance in the context of nurturing a community or nation. Despite the prevailing perception of male superiority in academic achievement, leadership, and professional careers, an intriguing trend emerges among school-level students, where female pupils exhibit a heightened interest relative to their male counterparts. In an endeavor to address this research gap, findings substantiate the argument, as supported by existing literature and data collected from ten Foreign English teachers working in government schools within the Tashkent region of Uzbekistan.

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